

Effect of planting date on tungro virus (RTV) incidence

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We studied the effect of planting date on RTV incidence in 1984-85 kharif. The field trial was in randomized block design with four replications and seven treatments. Twenty-five-day-old IR50 seedlings were planted in 9-m² plots at 20- × 10-cm spacing at 10-d intervals beginning 20 May. Plots received a basal 50-11-41.5 kg NPK/ha and 50 kg N/ha was topdressed in equal splits 15 and 35 days after transplanting (DT). No plant protection measures were taken.

RTV incidence at 45 DT by the Standard evaluation system for rice, green leafhopper (GLH) collected in a light trap from 0 to 30 DT, and grain yield were recorded (see table). Early plantings had lowest RTV incidence. Jun-Jul crops were severely infected and yielded low. There was a large GLH outbreak in Jul and Aug. *☞*

Effect of planting time on RTV incidence, 1984-85 kharif, Tirur, India.

Planting date	GLH light trap catch (no.) 0-30 DT	RTV (%) 45 DT	Yield (t/ha)
20 May 1984	381	2	3.1
30 May	936	3	4.0
10 Jun	39,453	51	2.2
20 Jun	54,625	65	1.7
30 Jun	151,496	74	0.8
10 Jul	170,158	82	0.6
20 Jul	160,400	86	0.9

Bacterial blight (BE) pathotype in Haryana

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BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* occurs in kresiek and blight forms in Haryana. The blight form is most serious in Kurukshetra, Karnal, and Ambala Districts. Two BB

Reactions^a of BB differentials to BB isolates, Kaul, India.

Variety	Known reaction to		Reaction			
	Pathotype I	Pathotype II	Blight, 1982	Blight, 1983	Kresiek, 1984	Blight
CAS209	—	—	S	S	S	S
DV85	R	S	R	MR (5)	MR (5)	—
IR1545-339-2-2	MS-S	S	S	S	S	S
IR20	MS-S	S	S	—	S	S
IR8	S	S	S	S	S	S
Jaya 14	—	—	S	S	R	S
Kinmaze	—	—	S	S	MS	—
Kogyoku	S	S	R	R	—	S
TN1	S	S	S	S	S	S
Nigeria 5	—	—	R	S	R	—
Tetep	—	—	—	MR (5)	S	S
Wase Aikoku	S	R	S	—	—	S
Malagkit Sungsong	MS-S	R	—	—	—	S
Cemposelak	MS-S	R	S	—	—	S
Chugoku 45	S	R	—	—	S	S
Sayaphal	R	R	—	—	—	R

^a All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Program results; — = not tested, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible.

pathotypes have been identified at the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad.

We sought to identify the BB pathotype in Haryana. In 1982-84, BB differential varieties were inoculated

with naturally occurring BB inoculum by clipping. Disease incidence was recorded 14 d after inoculation using the Standard evaluation system for rice. Reactions indicated that pathotype 1 is dominant (see table). *☞*

Pest Control and Management

INSECTS

Interspecific hybridization between four green leafhopper (GLH) species

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We studied interspecific hybridization between temperate *Nephotettix cincticeps* (NC) and three tropical GLH species: *N. virescens* (NV), *N. nigropictus* (NN) and *N. malavanus* (NM). Insects were reared on susceptible Nipponbare, at 25° C.

Direct and reciprocal crosses were made by placing a pair of newly emerged adults of 2 species inside a 20- × 170-mm test tube with a 30-d-old rice seedling. Eggs laid were counted and incubated on moist filter paper in a petri dish, and nymphs that hatched were reared individually until adults emerged. External and internal morphological characters of emerged adults were

Fertility of interspecific crosses between 4 GLH species, Kyoto, Japan.

Cross	Total eggs laid	Total eggs hatched	Hatching (%)
Female/male ^a			
NC/NC	92	87	94
NV/NV	118	111	94
NN/NN	93	87	93
NM/NM	81	84	96
NV/NN	38	26	68
NN/NV	36	7	19
NV/NC	49	30	61
NC/NV	14	0	0
NV/NM	80	13	16
NM/NV	42	11	26
NN/NC	27	4	15
NC/NN	25	0	0
NN/NM	18	0	0
NM/NN	58	12	21
NC/NM	48	9	19
NM/NC	45	10	22

^a NC = *N. cincticeps*, NV = *N. virescens*, NN = *N. nigropictus*, NM = *N. malayanus*.

compared with those of the parents.

Among parental crosses, NV laid the most eggs, but NM eggs had highest

Morphology of the head capsule and male genitalia of 4 GLH species and their interspecific hybrids. NC = *N. cincticeps*, NV = *N. virescens*, NN = *N. nigropictus*, NM = *N. malayanus*.

hatchability percentage (see table). Of 12 interspecific crosses, 9 produced hybrid progeny. Females from crosses with NC females and NN and NV males and crosses between NN females and NM males laid sterile eggs. Hatching percentage was generally low among

interspecific crosses. Eggs from crosses of NV females and NN males had the highest hatchability percentage (68%). Although crosses of NV females and NC males had 61% hatching percentage, the reciprocal cross produced no fertile eggs.

The figure compares external

morphology of the head capsule and the internal structure of the aedeagus and style of the male genitalia of hybrid adults with those of their parents. Hybrid external morphology and genitalia were intermediate between those of the parents. *S*

Intraspecific and interspecific feeding of whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) predators

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In rice ecosystems, predators help keep WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) populations below economic thresholds. Major predators include wolf spider *Lycosa pseudoannulata* Boes et Str. (Lycosidae: Araneae), mirid bug *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* Reuter (Hemiptera: Miridae), ladybird beetle *Synharmonia octomaculata* (F.) (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae), and rove

beetle *Paederus fuscipes* Curt. (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae).

Because predators feed on more than one insect species, we studied the extent to which the four adult predators feed on their own species. Each test lasted 5 d. Mortality of predators and prey was recorded daily, and dead insects were replaced after each observation.

When 10 *L. pseudoannulata* were caged together, they were cannibalistic and had 24% mortality. When 10 *C. lividipennis*, *S. octomaculata*, or *P. fuscipes* were caged with 1 *L. pseudoannulata*, the spider killed 60% of the *C. lividipennis* but no *S.*

Feeding rate per day of adult predator on fourth-instar WBPH,^a IRRI, 1985.

Predator	Predators released (no.)	<i>S. furcifera</i> mortality/predator per day
<i>Lycosa pseudoannulata</i>	1	5.9 a
<i>Cyrtorhinus lividipennis</i>	5	1.4 d
<i>Synharmonia octomaculata</i>	3	2.4 b
<i>Paedems fuscipes</i>	5	1.9 c
Check	—	0.2 e

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. Av of 5 observations recorded daily and 4 replications. Sixteen WBPH nymphs were released with a mouth aspirator. Dead predators and prey were replaced daily after each observation.